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Conductive Nanoparticle Enhancements for Structural Dielectric Capacitors

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Motivation and approaches

Concept of structural dielectric capacitors (SDCs)

- Energy stored by *interfacial polarization* of dielectric materials
- Carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRP)-based electrodes
- Dielectric materials, e.g. polymer films and **graphene oxide (GO)** films

Research problem

- Electrically insulating polymer used for matrix
- Resistance of CFRP based electrode increased

Approaches

- Addition of different concentrations of AuNPs

- Particle size: ~2 to 5 nm
- Highly crystalline
- Evenly dispersed

Electrical properties

- Electrical conductivity increased by ~15 – 250%
- Specific capacitance increased by ~10 – 150%
- Energy density increased by ~15 – 55%
- Best performance achieved by 0.5wt% AuNPs modified SDCs

Electron transfer via electron tunneling

At the highest concentration (1wt%) of AuNPs

- Substantial agglomerations
- Dilution of the average concentration
- No further increase in electrical conductivity

Mechanical properties

- Both hardener molecules and epoxy monomer absorbed on the surface of AuNP
- Increased the complexity
- Restricted localized movements

Cyan: DGEBA (epoxy monomer)

Purple: POPDA (hardener molecule)

Blue: DETA (hardener molecule)

Red: TEPA (hardener molecule)

Yellow: Au atoms of the AuNP

Intrinsic toughening of AuNPs/epoxy

- Ultimate stiffness of AuNPs: ~ 100 GPa
- Stiffness of epoxy: ~ 3 GPa
- Young's modulus increased by $\sim 1.5 - 7\%$
- Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) increased by $\sim 2 - 24\%$
- Best performance achieved by 1wt% AuNPs modified SDC

Conclusion

- This study highlighted the potential of the approach of doping CFRP-based electrodes with AuNPs to enhance both electrical and mechanical properties of SDC composites
- The optimum concentration of AuNPs in this study is 0.5wt%, at which some agglomeration occurs

Electric vehicles and unmanned aerial vehicles applications

- High strength-to-weight ratio of AuNPs modified SDCs decrease vehicle weight by ~60% compared to conventional structural materials, such as steel and aluminum
- Energy storage ability could replace the conventional battery in vehicle, further decrease vehicle weight by ~15%

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